

Minimal Information Versus Extremization of Entropy Subject to Constraints

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Maximization of entropy subject to constraints is a procedure used in the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases. We suggest, however, that this is a formal math procedure and must be examined in more detail. For example, if one has the two constraints: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, then there are many solutions $\{p(e_i)\}$, i.e. various different functions of e_i . Consider any one of these functions, called $p_1(e_i)$. One may immediately write: $h(p_1(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where h is the inverse function of p . Next, one may multiply by $dp(e_i)$ and integrate. Then: $d/dp(e_i) \int dp h(p(e_i)) = -1/T d/dp(e_i) \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. This is formally a maximization of entropy procedure, but it holds for each different $p(e_i)$ function. In each case, $p(e_i)$ and $h(p(e_i))$ differ, but all follow an extremization subject to constraints process.

The key, we argue, is to find a minimal information solution. In other words, even though any of the $p(e_i)$ may be written in terms of extremization, only one set represents only the information of the constraints. We have argued in previous notes that one may create a function $G = \sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ such that: $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ and $dG = \sum_i c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$. In other words, the differentials of the constraints actually yield the minimal information $p(e_i)$. This approach works for the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases, but in the Kaniadakis case, even though entropy density is formally written as: $\sum_i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ and extremization is performed, only one constraint is essentially used, namely $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. Thus, one does not have a sense of minimal information as in the Tsallis and Maxwell-Boltzmann cases, we argue. Instead, the distribution follows from the statement: $\int b dp \ln k(p/a) = p(e_i) \ln k(p)$ which is converted into a differential equation using d/dp . This equation does not follow from maximization of entropy. Instead the maximization of entropy equation which appears in (1) only contains one constraint $(e-u)/T$ (where u is the chemical potential) unlike the MB and Tsallis cases.

Constraints and Extremization

Given two constraints:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad ((1a)) \text{ and } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave} \quad ((1b))$$

one may find various different $p(e_i)$ functions which satisfy ((1a)) and ((1b)). Consider any of these solutions, which we call $p_1(e_i)$. One may write:

$$h(p_1(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ where } h \text{ is the inverse function of } p \quad ((2))$$

Next one may multiply by $dp(e_i)$ and integrate yielding:

$$\sum_i \int h(p_1(e_i)) dp_1(e_i) = -1/T \sum_i e_i p_1(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Taking $d/dp(e_i)$ of both sides of ((3)) yields: $p_1(e_i)$ as a solution of an extremization equation subject to a constraint. This extremization, however, holds for all solutions of ((1a)) and ((1b)) and so one does not find a minimal information one. Thus, we argue, one must be careful when writing extremization with respect to constraint equations. What is needed is a minimal information $p(e_i)$ function.

Minimal Information Based on Constraints

We have argued in previous notes that one way to find a minimal information solution is to create an entropy function $\text{Sum over } i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ which contains only the information of the two constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)). Because one uses two constraints with $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, one obtains a condition on $dh(p(e_i))/dp(e_i)$ which allows one to solve for $h(p(e_i))$ explicitly and hence obtain $p(e_i)$ as the inverse. This is different from using only one constraint as in ((2)) and ((3)), even though formally an extremization process is used.

Maxwell-Boltzmann case: $dG = d \text{Sum over } i p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) = -1/T \text{Sum over } i e_i dp(e_i) + 1 \text{Sum over } i dp(e_i)$ ((4))

Then: $p dh/dp = 1$ or $h = \ln(p)$ ((5))

Tsallis case: The energy constraint is now $\text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)^q$. Then:

$dG = d \text{Sum over } i p(e_i)^q h(p(e_i)) = -1/T \text{Sum over } i e_i d[p(e_i)^q] + 1 \text{Sum over } i d[p(e_i)^q]$ ((6))

$p(e_i)^q dh/dp(e_i) = 1$ or $h(p(e_i)) = c_1 + p(e_i)^{-q+1}$ ((7))

Kaniadakis Case

Formally, the Kaniadakis case seems to mirror the MB and Tsallis ones, but something different seems to be happening with respect to extremization of entropy subject to constraints. We follow the procedure of (1). Formally, one has:

$h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (just like in the MB and Tsallis cases) ((8a))

Furthermore, according to (1): entropy density = $\text{Sum over } i p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$ ((8b))

Note: (1) uses $n(e_i)$ instead of $p(e_i)$ and introduces a chemical potential. We use $p(e_i)$ and set the chemical potential to 0 here for simplicity.

(1) Starts with the notion $\exp_k(x)$ and so the inverse $\ln_k(x)$ is known, where $x = -e_i/T$.

In (1), it is noted that:

$$d/dp(e_i) \{ \sum \text{over } i \text{ Integral } dp(e_i) b \ln_k(p/a) - 1/T e_i p(e_i) \} = 0 \quad ((9a))$$

$$p(e_i) = a \exp_k(-e_i/(Tb)) \quad ((9b)) \quad (\text{Note: } \ln_k \text{ and } \exp_k \text{ are inverse functions.})$$

((9)) is an extremization equation subject to a constraint as pointed out in (1), but this is the type of extremization discussed in ((2)) and ((3)). It is not necessarily a minimal informational one. In particular, it holds for any \ln_k , \exp_k set of inverse functions.

((1)) then suggests that one keep only solutions for which:

$$\text{Integral } b \, dp \, \ln_k(p/a) = p(e_i) \ln_k(p) \quad (\text{Here } \ln_k(p) = h(p)) \quad ((10))$$

Here b and a are constants. Thus, ((10)) is the key equation for obtaining the explicit form of \ln_k and hence \exp_k (its inverse). ((10)), however, is not a maximization of entropy subject to a constraint equation, it is a completely independent condition, it seems. Thus, the Kaniadakis approach does not really follow from the extremization of entropy subject to a constraint, nor is it based on a minimal information of constraints result like the MB and Tsallis cases.

In particular, (1) essentially shows that a solution of ((10)) is

$$\ln_k(p) = 1/(2k) \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} \text{ if } a = (1-kk)^{1/(2k)} \quad ((11))$$

Note: (1) converts ((10)) into a differential equation before solving.

In particular, one could have started with ((10)) a priori and solved for the Kaniadakis result without even introducing the notion of extremization of entropy in the first place, unlike the Tsallis and MB situations in which the minimal information extremization approach directly yields the two distributions.

Conclusion

Kaniadakis, Tsallis and Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions are all presented in a framework in which one has $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where h is the inverse function of $p(e_i)$ and entropy density is $\sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) h(p(e_i))$. Furthermore, all three are presented in terms of maximization of entropy subject to constraints. There is a fundamental difference, however, In the MB and Tsallis cases, the maximization is based directly on the two constraints $\sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum \text{over } i \, e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$ (or $\sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i)^q e_i$ for the Tsallis case). In fact, there are many $p(e_i)$ which satisfy this result. If one only use the situation $h(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (which holds for the MB, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases), then multiplying by $dp(e_i)$ and integrating yields an equation which when operated on by $d/dp(e_i)$ returns $h(p(e_i))$. This, however, does not yield a solution for $p(e_i)$. In the Tsallis and MB cases, we argue that one has a minimal information function through the extremization: $dG = d \sum \text{over } i \, p(e_i) h(p(e_i)) = \sum \text{over } i \, c_i d(\text{constraint } i)$. This yields the actual distribution.

In the Kaniadakis case, one uses only one constraint in developing an extremization equation ((9a)) and so this holds for any h and its inverse $p(e_i)$. (1) then imposes equation ((10)), which is

not an extremization equation in order to obtain the solution of h and hence $p(e_i)$. In other words, one could have started directly with ((11)) to obtain the Kaniadakis distribution because one does not seem to be using a minimal information function like in the Tsallis and MB cases, we argue.

References

1. Kaniadakis, G. Statistical Mechanics in the Context of Special Relativity (2018)
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